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Building a Model Effecting of Leadership Skills on Performance

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Abstract:

The leader is the head of an organization, all activities, skills, of the leader affect the performance of the organization. Therefore, there have been many studies on leadership skills. However, research on leadership skills associated with the level of supply chain participation of enterprises is still very limited. From the results of the review of related studies, the article proposes a research model to evaluate the influence of leadership skills on the performance of Vietnamese enterprises.

Keywords: Leadership skills, operational efficiency, Vietnamese enterprises

1. Introduction

Business efficiency is always the top concern of all businesses, because business efficiency reflects the ability to combine input factors, allowing to minimize costs in business activities. to achieve profit goals. Thereby, business performance will reflect the leader's ability to perform the leadership function in the enterprise, the ability to use resources to accomplish goals and achieve the highest efficiency in operations. Therefore, businesses are constantly improving and improving business efficiency, especially in the context of increasingly fierce global competition today.

The fact shows that there are many factors affecting the business performance of enterprises, of which factors related to leaders are considered to have a significant influence on the business performance of enterprises. Leaders are indispensable in any business, whether large or small, in the field of manufacturing or providing services, not only that, leaders also influence the satisfaction and performance of the people they lead (Bass, 1990) and leaders appear at all levels of a firm's organizational structure.

Among the factors of leadership, leadership skills are considered as one of the most important factors. Because, leadership skills are the ability to perform tasks, turn knowledge into actions of leaders, and demonstrate the leader's proficiency in applying acquired knowledge in practice. leadership functions to achieve the set goals. Leaders in the enterprise have to perform many different functions and tasks, so they need many different skills.

2. Research model and research hypotheses

Depending on different approaches and different research subjects, the authors propose many different skills of leaders that affect business performance of enterprises. However, the above skills are still fragmentary, incomplete and not strictly systematized, therefore, the study proposes to use the components of leadership skills to assess leadership skills.

In three research models on the components of leadership skills by Mumford, M. D. et al (2000) quite comprehensively, assessing leadership skills in many different aspects. However, this model is quite complex, requires many people to perform, takes a lot of time and effort, so it is difficult to implement within the scope of an individual conducting this study.

Meanwhile, the leadership components of Katz (1955) and Mumford, Campion and Morgeson (2007) are quite simple, easy to use, and have many similar skills, but have a method. different division.

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The components of leadership skills by Katz (1955) can be considered as the first model to study in-depth leadership skills, this model was born in 1955, a period when the economy had not yet developed. as powerful and complex as it is today. At the same time, Katz (1955) uses the term "technical skill" to assess a leader's understanding of activities related to specific methods, processes, procedures, or techniques in certain areas such as production, finance, sales, etc. This has more or less created misunderstandings for many leaders.

The components of leadership skills of Mumford, Campion and Morgeson (2007) were just born in 2007, based on the synthesis and separation of previous research on leadership skills, and models. This model is tending to be popular and widely used in recent years, and at the same time, this model assesses the skills of leaders more clearly than the two models presented above. Besides, the textile industry Vietnamese garment develops mainly in the direction of outsourcing, the vast majority of Vietnamese textile and garment enterprises are small and medium-sized enterprises, limited liability companies are the main ones, the ability of leaders is still limited. Therefore, the components of leadership skills of Mumford, Campion and Morgeson (2007) proved the most suitable to assess leadership skills of Vietnamese textile and garment enterprises in three models of structural elements. leadership skills.

From the above analysis, the study proposes to use the four components of leadership skills of Mumford, Campion and Morgeson (2007) to measure and evaluate the skills of leaders in Vietnamese textile and garment enterprises. .

- The first is the group of cognitive skills.

This skill is related to the basic cognitive abilities of the leader. Talking skills enable leaders to communicate effectively about what needs to be done and why it is needed. to be done. Listening skills help leaders gain a comprehensive understanding of the wants and problems of others, and reading comprehension helps leaders understand complex written information. Active learning skills enable leaders to work with new information and grasp its implications. These skills enable leaders to adapt behaviors and strategies to deal with the urgent, infrequent, and dynamic elements of their work. And finally, critical thinking skills allow leaders to fully and rationally analyze the strengths and limitations of different approaches to work, thereby helping the leader to make informed decisions. sound decision.

- Second is the group of skills to work with people.

According to Katz (1955), people skills help leaders understand, motivate and motivate individuals and groups in the enterprise. People skills are social skills and people skills that are related to interacting with and influencing others to achieve business goals (Katz, 1955; Mumford, Marks et al., 2000). Right in the concept of leadership "leadership is the process of influence..." shows that people skills are very important and have a great influence on business performance of enterprises.

Today, leaders must constantly deal with internal and external conflicts of the business, leaders work in an interactive world environment, the interaction of each other. Therefore, leaders need to devote to building community, resolving polarization, creating strong linkages between departments within the business, and linking the business with external systems. To perform these tasks, leaders require social skills. Because, social awareness allows the leader to understand the reactions of others (possibly a higher-ranking leader). , colleagues, subordinates, customers, suppliers, and other organizations outside the business) and understand why others act as they do. On that basis, the leader will come up with appropriate strategies and actions to combine his actions with the actions of others (coordination skills), helping the leader to reconcile the differences. and establish a harmonious relationship between different actors (negotiation skills). At the same time, a leader with persuasion skills will influence others to more effectively carry out the organization's goals.

- The third skill is the group of business skills.

These skills are those related to the specific functional activities of leaders, including: skills in analyzing activities in the business, skills related to human resource management, skills related to the management of financial resources and skills related to the management of the physical resources of the business.

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The skills of business analysis allow leaders to grasp the business activities of the business. From there, better meet customer needs, improve production processes, improve progress in production and business activities and improve the efficiency in production and business of enterprises.

Skill in managing the physical resources of the business is important for leaders in making decisions about the procurement and allocation of the right machinery, technology, and materials in the implementation. This makes a great contribution to the effective use of material resources of the enterprise, and contributes to improving and enhancing the business efficiency of the enterprise.

Human resource is one of the important resources of an enterprise, and an important functional activity that leaders must perform is human resource management. Human resource management skills allow leaders to identify suitable personnel for the job, motivate employees, develop employees and create conditions for career advancement for employees. This has a great influence on the job satisfaction of employees, increases productivity and contributes to improving business efficiency of enterprises.

An indispensable functional activity in any business is financial management. Financial management skills help leaders use the company's financial resources effectively, thereby contributing to increasing revenue, reducing costs and increasing profits for the business.

- The fourth skill is the group of strategic skills.

The leader has to perform a number of tasks such as: building a vision and setting goals; planning and developing action programs; make changes in accordance with the changes of the environment, ensuring the existence and development of enterprises (Gardner, J.W., 1988). To accomplish these tasks, leaders require strategic skills, because these skills involve a comprehensive understanding of the organization's operations, allowing leaders to have a vision. perspective, allowing leaders to understand complex issues, resolve ambiguity and ambiguity, and create impact within the organization. Specifically like:

The skill of building a systematic vision and awareness of the business will involve planning the basics of the business, allowing the leader to build the image of the business in the future, and identifying when material changes to the business have occurred or are likely to occur.

The skill to identify the consequences and identify the main causes of the problem is related to understanding the operating environment of the business, helping the leader to understand the cause-and-effect relationship in achieving the results. long-term results of the business. This, in turn, allows leaders to identify a causal pattern that includes key elements and relationships within the leader's specific environment. This allows leaders to recognize relationships. relationships between problems and opportunities, and choosing appropriate strategies to address them.

In addition, problem identification skills allow the leader to identify the true nature of the problems facing the business. In addition, the re-evaluation of solutions carried out allows the leader to examine effectiveness of solutions, as well as the basis for leaders to draw lessons from experience in proposing solutions in the future. Strategic skills not only help leaders achieve effective results. business performance in the present, but also aimed at achieving business performance in the future.

From the above analysis, the author proposes a detailed research model and research hypotheses as follows:

Figure 1. Research model

- Hypothesis H1: Cognitive skills have an influence and influence in the same direction as the business performance of Vietnamese textile and garment enterprises.
- Hypothesis H2: Skills in working with people have an influence and influence in the same direction as the business performance of Vietnamese textile and garment enterprises.
- Hypothesis H3: Business skills have an influence and influence in the same direction as the business performance of Vietnamese textile and garment enterprises.
- Hypothesis H4: Strategic skills have an influence and influence in the same direction as the business performance of Vietnamese textile and garment enterprises.
- Hypothesis H5: Innovation skills have an influence and influence in the same direction as the business performance of Vietnamese textile and garment enterprises.

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- Hypothesis H6: Cognitive skills have an influence and influence in the same direction as Organizational Supply Chain Participation
- Hypothesis H7: Skills to work with people have an influence and influence in the same direction as the organization's Supply Chain Participation
- Hypothesis H8: Business skills have an influence and influence in the same direction as the Organization's Supply Chain Participation
- Hypothesis H9: Strategic skills have an influence and influence in the same direction as Organization's Supply Chain Participation
- Hypothesis H10: Innovation skills have an influence and influence in the same direction as the Organization's Supply Chain Participation.
- Hypothesis H11: The level of organization's supply chain involvement has a positive impact on business performance

3. Conclusion

The study has reviewed leadership skills, the theoretical basis of business performance of enterprises, and the influence of leadership skills on business performance of enterprises.

Regarding leadership and leadership skills, agreeing with some authors, the study said that:

Leadership is the process of influencing others to understand and agree on what needs to be done and how to do it, and the process of facilitating individual and collective efforts. in order to achieve common goals. A leader is a person who holds a position in an enterprise, performs the leadership function in the enterprise, and realizes the goals of the enterprise through influencing others.

- Leadership skills are the ability to perform tasks, turn knowledge into actions of the leader, and demonstrate the leader's proficiency in applying acquired knowledge to actual functions. leadership to achieve set goals.

Regarding business performance of enterprises, on the basis of analyzing different approaches to business efficiency, the research suggests that business performance of enterprises is a reflection of the combination of input factors, allows to minimize the costs in business activities to achieve the profit goal of the business. When determining the criteria to measure the business performance of the enterprise, the enterprise should pay attention to some characteristics and some requirements for the business performance measurement criteria of the enterprise.

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